

TENSILE, COMPRESSIVE AND SHEAR RESIDUAL STRENGTHS OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO BALLISTIC IMPACT WITH DIFFERENT VELOCITIES

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Symbols and Abbreviation

A_d	Detected overall damage area
C	Calibre of projectile
d_e	$d_e = (4 A_d / \pi)^{0.5}$, equivalent diameter for damage area expression
d_0	Characteristic distance
E_{xx}	Modulus of laminate in x (0-ply) direction
E_{yy}	Modulus of laminate in y (90-ply) direction
G_{xy}	In-plane shear Modulus of laminate
F	Finite width correction factor
K_T	Stress concentration factor
N/A	Not applicable
R	Radius of a machined hole
R^2	Correlation coefficient
S	Lamina in-plane shear strength
Tap	Tap test
TG	Thermography damage detection
v_i	Impact speed of projectile
v_r	Residual speed of projectile after perforation
v_{50}	Ballistic limit speed
v_{50est}	Ballistic limit speed estimated using Eqn.1
ν_{xy}	Lamina in-plane Poisson ratio
W	Width of specimen
X	Lamina longitudinal strength
Y	Lamina lateral strength
σ	Normal stress
σ_0	Limit remote normal stress, un-notched specimen
σ_n	Limit remote normal stress, notched specimen
τ_0	Limit remote shear stress, un-notched specimen
τ_n	Limit remote shear stress, un-notched specimen
τ_{xy}	In plane shear stress

1 Introduction

Fibre-reinforced polymer composite materials are increasingly used in many aircraft. Some recently developed military helicopters, such as Bell/Boeing V22 and H-53K, as well as Eurocopter Tiger, and NHI's NH90, have nearly all-composite airframe structures. Unlike civil operations, military aircraft are vulnerable to ballistic impact damage from

small-arms fire in the battlefield. Knowledge of ballistic damage to the carbon fibre polymer materials and the residual strengths of composite structures is important for military aircraft design, operation, and battle-damage repairs.

The vulnerability criteria currently used for metallic structures is the "damage limit" approach based on visible damage. In the case of composite structures, the damage caused by ballistic impact involves delamination in the laminate skins, debonding between the skins and honeycomb core, and core damage. This damage generally extends to a significantly larger area than the visible damage area, thus requiring detection using non-destructive inspection (NDI) techniques.

The residual strength of composite structure arising from a combination of visible penetration damage and invisible damage is not well understood.

Limited research has been reported in measurement of residual strengths of composite structures subject to ballistic damage [1-4]. This paper summarises recent research carried out at the Defence Science and Technology Organisation (DSTO) and the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures (CRC-ACS) in this area.

2 Experiment Method

2.1 Ballistic Testing and Structural Test Specimens

Projectiles with 7.62 mm, 12.7 mm and 20.0 mm calibres were used in the ballistic testing with relatively low and high impact speeds between 200 m/s and 1000 m/s. The impact and residual speeds of the projectile were measured using two chronographs installed in front of and behind the target, respectively.

Three types of structural test specimens, namely tensile, compression, and shear specimens were designed and manufactured.

For both tensile and compression specimens, large panels were made first. After ballistic impact, they were cut into the specified specimen sizes with the ballistic damage at the centre. Shear specimens were made in their final size before ballistic impact.

The laminate tensile specimens were made of carbon-epoxy prepreg with a layup of [(0/90)/(±45)]s. The size of the specimens was 250 mm x 100 mm.

The sandwich panel compression specimens were made using two face sheets with the same material and layup as the tensile specimen, co-cured to a 15 mm thick Nomex honeycomb core with a film adhesive. The size of the specimen was 150 mm x 100 mm.

The section view of the shear specimen is shown in Fig.1. The front view of a shear specimen in the test fixture is shown in Fig 3. The prepreg, honeycomb core and adhesive materials are the same as those used for the compression specimens. The layups of top and bottom skins are [(0/90)/(±45)/(0/90)] and [(0/90)/(±45)]s, respectively. The bottom skin represents the external surface. Ballistic impact was conducted after the specimens were made.

The material property data used in the analysis are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Laminate material properties

Properties		Lamina (25°C)	Honeycomb
Modulus (GPa)	E11	62	0.002
	E22	60	0.002
	E33	9.5	0.128
	G12	4.9	0.0008
	G13	4.9	0.0365
	G23	4.9	0.0214
Poisson Ratio	λ12	0.09	0.3
	λ13	0.09	0.016
	λ23	0.30	0.016
Strength (MPa)	σ11	800	-
	σ22	800	-
	σ33	-	2.17
	τ12	100	-
	τ13	70	1.10
	τ23	70	0.62
Thickness (mm)		0.225	15

Fig.1. Shear specimen (mm)

The ballistic limit speed of the laminate and sandwich panels, v_{50} , was estimated using Eqn.1 [5] with the measured ballistic impact and residual speeds, approximately 40 and 56 m/s, respectively.

$$v_{50est} = (v_i^2 - v_r^2)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

2.2 NDI Measurement

Tap test, ultrasonic A-scan and flash thermography non-destructive inspection (NDI) techniques were used to examine the extent of damage caused by ballistic impact to the specimens.

The boundary lines of the damage area marked from the tap test and ultrasonic A-scan, and the images from the flash thermography NDI were processed using an image processing program, IMAGEJ, [6] to quantify the total damage areas.

An equivalent diameter, d_e , is calculated from the measured damage area to provide a convenient method of comparison.

2.3 Structural Testing

The tensile specimen was installed in the test machine with a 50 mm gripping length at each end (Fig.2(a)).

(a) Tensile test

(b) Compression test

Fig.2. Tensile and compression tests. A pristine specimen with end reinforcement is shown in (b)

During compression testing, the impacted specimens were compressed directly between two platens of the test machine from both ends. The experiment proved that the compression failure was neither in the form of globe buckling nor face sheet wrinkle. For the undamaged (baseline) specimens, additional end reinforcement was found necessary to prevent premature failure at the ends and thus enable the true compression strength of these specimens to be measured. These specimens were made with 15 mm extra length at each end (Fig.2(b)). After manufacture, the ends were encapsulated in a resin casting (AW106/ HY953 with 5% by weight DT082 filler (calcium carbonate)). The specimens with end reinforcement failed at their mid section with 6.7% increase of failure load on average compared with those without end reinforcement.

The shear test was conducted on a picture frame test fixture with four hinges, Fig.3. The specimen was bolted to the frame. The load was applied diagonally through two hinges.

Both tensile and compression tests were conducted on a 100kN Instron tensile test machine, with a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The shear test was conducted on a 500kN Instron tensile test machine with a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min.

Fig.3. Picture frame shear test

3 NDI Results

Comparison of the detected damage areas from tap test, ultrasonic A-scan and flash thermography NDI techniques is provided in Tables 2 and 3.

As shown in these two tables, the tap test and flash thermography agreed reasonably well, with the tap test showing slightly larger damage area. The A-scan device used a 6 mm diameter probe that was

unable to pick up small delaminations from the edge of the perforation. For larger damage areas, the tap test and A-scan had better agreement.

Table 2. NDI method comparison – Laminate specimens

C (mm)	d _e Entrance (mm)			d _e Exit (mm)		
	TG	Tap	A-scan	TG	Tap	A-scan
7.62	13.0	14.4	*	16.2	16.7	*
7.62	13.4	14.2	*	15.8	16.0	*
12.7	17.7	19.2	*	24.1	24.9	*
12.7	18.0	21.0	*	22.5	24.0	*
12.7	18.5	19.5	*	20.4	21.0	*
20.0	-	28.1	27.6	-	30.7	28.8
20.0	-	27.0	28.2	-	28.6	29.3
20.0	-	28.7	28.4	-	29.4	29.4
20.0	-	27.2	28.7	-	30.1	30.2

* Unable to determine damage reliably beyond visible damage
- No measurement was conducted

Table 3. NDI method comparison – Sandwich specimens

C (mm)	d _e Entrance (mm)			d _e Exit (mm)		
	TG	Tap	A-scan	TG	Tap	A-scan
7.62	13.6	14.2	10.9	20.0	21.9	11.5
7.62	15.2	14.4	10.9	19.8	20.7	11.6
7.62	-	15.7	14.3	-	18.3	15.3
7.62	-	14.8	13.6	-	18.6	15.8
12.7	22.3	22.7	18.1	24.8	26.5	19.4
12.7	26.7	27.5	18.5	27.2	29.7	25.3
12.7	21.8	23.2	18.2	25.5	26.6	20.9
12.7	-	23.8	23.4	-	23.4	24.3
12.7	-	22.6	25.0	-	24.5	25.0

Tables 4 and 5 provide damage areas corresponding to different calibres and different nominal impact speeds, detected using the tap test.

As shown in these two tables, in several cases the damage caused by lower impact speed is lower than caused by higher impact speed, however, in two cases (7.62 mm calibre, exit side in Table 3 and 12.7 mm calibre, exit side in Table 4), the opposite was true.

The results showed that the overall damage area is significantly higher than the projectile calibre size. The maximum damage (exit side) data in Tables 3 and 4 were fitted using the following polynomial formula as a function of the projectile calibre, C:

$$d_{e(exit)} = k_1 C^2 + k_2 C + k_3 \quad (2)$$

where k_1 , k_2 and k_3 are constants.

For laminate specimens, k_1 , k_2 and k_3 are 0.0019, 1.00 and 8.91, and for sandwich specimens k_1 , k_2 and k_3 are 0.112, -0.771 and 18.1. In both cases, a high correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.95$ is achieved. Thus the damage area appears predominately affected by the calibre size as the effect of the impact speed, when it is significantly higher than the ballistic limit, is insignificant.

Table 4. Tap test detected damage under various nominal impact speeds – Laminate specimens

C (mm)	d_e Entrance (mm)			d_e Exit (mm)		
	840 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s	840 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s
7.62	14.4	14.5	13.2	16.7	16.8	16.7
	14.2	14.1	12.8	16.0	16.2	16.3
	-	10.8	12.7	-	16.3	18.2
C (mm)	d_e Entrance (mm)			d_e Exit (mm)		
	660 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s	660 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s
12.7	19.2	-	17.7	24.9	-	21.0
	21.0	-	18.1	24.0	-	20.8
	19.5	-	18.3	21.0	-	19.9
C (mm)	d_e Entrance (mm)			d_e Exit (mm)		
	1000 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s	1000 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s
20.0	28.1	-	-	30.7	-	-
	27.0	-	-	28.6	-	-
	28.7	-	-	29.4	-	-
	27.2	-	-	30.1	-	-

Table 5. Tap test detected damage under various nominal impact speeds – Sandwich specimens

C (mm)	d_e Entrance (mm)			d_e Exit (mm)		
	840 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s	840 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s
7.62	14.2	18.2	15.7	21.9	19.0	18.3
	14.4	14.3	14.8	20.7	19.0	18.6
	-	-	14.4	-	-	18.0
	-	-	14.4	-	-	16.1
	-	-	15.3	-	-	17.1
C (mm)	d_e Entrance (mm)			d_e Exit (mm)		
	660 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s	660 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s
12.7	22.7	20.0	23.8	26.5	27.1	27.0
	27.5	19.3	22.6	29.7	26.0	26.7
	23.2	20.7	22.5	26.6	24.9	27.9
	-	20.6	20.6	-	25.1	24.7
	-	21.2	26.0	-	24.8	30.1
	-	20.3	21.7	-	24.5	24.7
C (mm)	d_e Entrance (mm)			d_e Exit (mm)		
	1000 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s	1000 m/s	400 m/s	220 m/s
20.0	41.9	-	-	48.6	-	-
	37.8	-	-	48.4	-	-

4 Tensile and Compression Test Results and Processing

The residual strengths measured from the tensile and compression tests are listed in Tables 6 and 7. Test results from pristine specimens and specimens with machined holes are also included for comparison.

The results showed that the strengths of the specimen with ballistic damage were significantly lower than that of the pristine specimens, however, they were only slightly lower than that of the specimens with a machined hole of the same diameter as the projectile calibre in terms of the average strength.

The results overall did not indicate a clear trend of the effect of the impact speed on the residual strength.

Table 6. Residual strength from laminate specimen tensile tests

Specimen Type	Impact Speed (m/s)	Failure Load (kN)	Average Failure Load (kN)
Pristine	N/A	44.8	45.0
		44.6	
		47.7	
		42.7	
8 mm diameter machined hole	N/A	30.8	30.8
		30.5	
		31.2	
7.62 mm calibre ballistic impact	845	31.5	30.3
	844	29.8	
	845	29.7	
7.62 mm calibre ballistic impact	224	30.4	30.5
	234	30.5	
12.7 mm dia. machined hole	N/A	27.4	27.0
		26.5	
12.7 mm calibre ballistic impact	666	24.8	25.7
	662	27.8	
	665	24.4	
12.7 mm calibre ballistic impact	204	23.7	25.8
	236	29.9	
	249	23.8	
20 mm calibre ballistic impact	998	20.3	20.6
	1000	20.1	
	1004	21.5	

Table 7. Residual strength from sandwich specimen compression tests

Specimen Type	Impact Speed (m/s)	Failure Load (kN)	Average Failure Load (kN)
Pristine	N/A	65.2	65.1
		67.8	
		62.2	
8 mm diameter machined hole	N/A	45.6	47.2
		44.3	
		51.8	
7.62 mm calibre ballistic impact	848	47.6	47.2
	848	46.8	
7.62 mm calibre ballistic impact	231	42.9	41.0
	230	39.0	
12.7 mm dia. machined hole	N/A	40.8	40.5
		40.4	
		40.2	
12.7 mm calibre ballistic impact	670	38.7	37.9
	668	37.3	
	670	37.8	
12.7 mm calibre ballistic impact	191	36.5	39.5
	231	42.9	
	230	39.0	

The characteristic distance approach developed by Whitney and Nuismer [7-8] was applied to predict the strength of the specimens with machined holes under tensile and compression loads using the following formula:

$$\frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_0} = 2F / [2 + \xi^2 + 3\xi^4 - (K_T - 3)(5\xi^6 - 7\xi^8)] \quad (3)$$

where $\xi = R / (R + d_0)$

$$K_T = 1 + \{2[(E_{xx} / E_{yy})^{0.5} - \nu_{xy}] + (E_{xx} / G_{xy})\}^{0.5}$$

$$F = \frac{3(1 - 2R/W)}{2 + (1 - 2R/W)^3}$$

For the tensile test results, using Eqn.3 with the data in Table 6 for 8 mm and 12.7 mm machined holes, the characteristic distances can be determined. The results are plotted in Fig.4.

Using Fig.4 and the average values in Table 6, specimens with 7.62 mm and 12.7 mm calibre damage could be considered as equivalent to 7.92 mm and 15.3 mm diameter machined holes, respectively. The estimation of equivalent diameter

in the 20 mm calibre cases is not included as there is no data for the machined hole near 20 mm diameter.

Fig.4. Tensile strength of specimens with machined holes vs. pristine specimens ($d_0 = 0.186R + 1.56$ mm)

For ballistic damaged specimens, strictly speaking Eqn.3 can not be used to predict the strength. However, considering the delamination damage as a small perturbation from a clean hole damage, to establish an empirical formula through a regression approach with experimental data to predict the strength of the specimens with ballistic damage, Eqn.3 provides an effective model.

For the ballistic damaged specimens, Eqn.3 was used to fit the measured data by replacing R with $C/2$ and adjusting the characteristic distance. Fig.5 gives the plot for the tensile test results. The characteristic distance value is provided in the figure.

From Fig.5 considerable scatter can be seen in the strength of the ballistic damaged specimens.

Similarly for the compression test results, the characteristic distances $d_0 = 2.70$ mm and $d_0 = 0.0906C + 1.54$ mm are obtained for the specimens with machined holes and ballistic impact damage respectively.

Fig.5. Tensile strength of specimens with ballistic damage vs. pristine specimens
 $(R=C/2, d_0 = -0.00821C^2 + 0.208C + 1.10 \text{ mm})$

In order to obtain insight into the effects of ballistic damage, a linear elastic finite element method (FEM) analysis was further conducted (using MSC Nastran, 2008 R2). In this analysis, the focus was on the effect of delamination on the residual strength since it is considered that delamination constitutes the majority of damage that can only be detected by NDI means. A 3 mm delamination was assumed (based on the entrance hole diameter d_e shown in Table 4) between all layers for a perforation diameter of 12.7 mm. Each layer of the four layer specimen was modelled with two 20 node brick elements through thickness. The mesh is shown in Fig.6, with total number of 72,000 elements for the structure.

Fig.6. FEM mesh for a tensile test specimen

The applied load was in the form of remote stress along the boundary that corresponded to the tensile failure load for the ballistic impact case. For comparison a machined hole (without delamination) with the same remote stress was also calculated. These results are shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7. Comparison between stresses in layer 1 (upper) and layer 2 (lower)

The results in Fig.7 (upper) for layer 1 in the 0° fibre direction show that the stresses at the edge of the hole where failure occurs are higher (11%) for ballistic damage than for the case of the machined hole. In the case of layer 2, Fig.7 (lower), the stresses in the 45° fibre direction are higher in the case of the machined hole, however the maximum fibre stresses are considerably lower than the

stresses in layer 1. Although not shown, stresses in layers 4 and 3 are much the same as layers 1 and 2 respectively. The other stress components (such as in-plane shear or through thickness stresses) were low in comparison to the allowable stresses. Clearly delamination from ballistic damage results in a redistribution of load.

Though the above analysis considered a tensile load case, it would also be applicable to the compression load case since the failure from buckling or surface wrinkle was not involved.

5 Shear Test Results and Processing

The residual strengths measured from the shear tests are listed in Table 8. Test results from pristine specimens and specimens with machined holes are also included for comparison. This included an assessment of multiple penetrations of 12.7mm ballistic damage.

Fig.8 shows a tested specimen that failed in compression perpendicular to the tensile loading direction (-45° direction of the laminate). The crack is along the loading direction (45° direction of the laminate). The test specimens failed either in this way in compression, or in tension with the crack along the -45° direction of the laminate.

Fig.8. Compression failure of specimen loaded in shear, loading direction shown by white arrows

For the shear specimens, some penetrating points were not exactly at the centre location. The 20 mm round shots in particular were significantly off-centre. FEM analysis was conducted to examine the effect of the different damage locations on the strength of these specimens.

Table 8. Residual strength from shear tests

Specimen Type	Impact Speed (m/s)	Failure Load (kN)	Average Failure load (kN)
Pristine	N/A	113.7	120.7
		127.7	
8 mm diameter machined hole	N/A	94.0	92.6
		91.1	
7.62 mm calibre ballistic impact	845	96.2	92.9
	844	89.5	
12.7 mm calibre ballistic impact	666	79.4	81.2
	662	82.9	
12.7 mm calibre ballistic impact (two shots)	204	75.0	77.3
	236	79.5	
20 mm calibre ballistic impact	998	80.7	80.0
	1000	79.3	

The Nastran FEM program was used to model the shear rig and specimens. A 3D view of the FEM mesh is shown in Fig.9. Shell elements were used to model the laminate skins, while solid elements were used to model the Nomex honeycomb and the steel frame. In order to simplify the analysis the pivot was replaced by a link with rotational freedom at the hinge positions. The loading was applied diagonally through two hinges (a force applied to one corner point and fixed displacement at the other corner).

Fig.9. FEM model of shear frame and specimen of honeycomb sandwich composite

The FEM modelling indicated that, as expected, the critical layers were the -45° and +45° payers with nearly identical peak stress in compression and tension respectively, and that the bottom skin (refer

to Fig.1) withstands the majority of the applied load (79.3%).

In analysis conducted, a 20 mm hole at the centre of the panel and a 20 mm hole located in the corner of the panel (where a 20 mm round hit), Fig. 10, was compared.

The results plotted in Fig. 11 show that the shear stress of the bottom laminate at the corner location is lower by 14% than that at the centre.

Fig.10. Finite element mesh for rig and a specimen with a 20 mm hole at the corner

Fig.11. FEM comparison of laminate shear stress in corner and centre of the bottom skin (20 mm hole)
As an alternative to the FEM method, the characteristic distance approach developed by Tan [9-10] was adopted to model the strength of the

specimen with a machined hole under the shear loads.

The laminate stress distribution under an applied in-plane load can be obtained from a superposition of the stress components due to the uniform stress field and the stress concentration, using a set of complex equations provided in References [9-10]. The strength of the specimens can then be further determined using a suitable failure criterion with the characteristic length approach. The following Tsai-Hill criterion [11] was considered:

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X^2} - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{XY} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{Y^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad (4)$$

The equations were solved for a remote shear stress loading. As previously mentioned the failure occurred in the -45° degree plies in compression, or in the 45° degree plies in tension at almost the same load.

The result is shown in Fig.12 where the characteristic length was set at $d_0 = 1.0$ mm, from calibration with the experimental data of the specimens with an 8 mm diameter machined hole.

Fig.12. Shear strength of specimens with machined holes vs. pristine specimens ($d_0 = 1.0$ mm)

Unlike the characteristic distance approach developed by Whitney and Nuismer [7-8], Tan's approach does not provide a closed form analytical solution. Rather it requires use of the Mathematica program to solve a set of complex equations. For

easy use, the results from this model were further fitted using a polynomial equation:

$$\frac{\tau_n}{\tau_0} = k_1 R^5 + k_2 R^4 + k_3 R^3 + k_4 R^2 + k_5 R + k_6 \quad (5)$$

Where k_1 to k_6 are $-9.05E-10$, $2.46E-7$, $-2.61E-5$, $1.38E-3$, -0.0395 and 1.01 , respectively. The correlation coefficient $R^2 = 1.000$ (the fitted curve and original curve virtually overlap together).

A model similar to Eqn.5 is used to fit the measured strength data of the specimens with ballistic damage:

$$\frac{\tau_n}{\tau_0} = k_1 C^5 + k_2 C^4 + k_3 C^3 + k_4 C^2 + k_5 C + k_6 \quad (6)$$

k_1 to k_6 are 0 , 0 , $-1.47E-5$, $1.18E-3$, -0.0384 and 1.00 . The correlation coefficient $R^2=0.99$. The results are plotted in Fig.13. Note that the correction factor from the FEM analysis was included for the 20 mm data points.

Fig.13. Shear strength of specimens with ballistic damage vs. pristine specimens

Military aircraft structures may encounter multiple hits in adjacent areas. In a preliminary effort to investigate the effect of multi-hits, two 12.7 mm projectiles were impacted on each of two shear test specimen panels. As shown in Fig.14 the two shots are almost symmetric to the specimen centre, and around 30 mm apart (measured from the perforation

centres). The measured failure loads are included in Table 8.

Using the curve in Figure 13 and the ratio between the average failure load of these two specimens and that of the pristine specimens ($\tau_n/\tau_0 = 0.640$), the ballistic impact from the two 12.7 mm round impacts may be considered as equivalent to a single shot of 15.0 mm calibre projectile.

Fig.14. A shear specimen with impact from two 12.7 mm projectiles. Shot exit face is shown.

6 Summary and Conclusions

The NDI results indicated good agreement between the tap test and flash thermography damage measurement, with the tap test showing slightly larger detected damage area. The A-scan device was unable to pick up small delaminations from the edge of the perforation due to the probe size limit. For larger damage areas, the tap test and A-scan showed good agreement. The overall damage area is significantly larger than the projectile calibre size. The effect of the impact speed in the speed range tested is insignificant.

The measured residual strengths showed that the strengths of the specimens with ballistic damage were significantly lower than that of the pristine specimens, however, they are only slightly lower than that of the specimens with a machined hole of the same diameter as the projectile calibre. The results did not show a clear trend of the effect of the impact speed on the residual strength.

Considerable scatter was seen in the strength of the ballistic damaged specimens.

The characteristic distance approach developed by Whitney and Nuismer was used to simulate tensile

and compression strength of specimens with a machined hole and extended to simulate strength of specimens with ballistic damage. The model fitted the mean values of measurement data well.

Delamination at the ballistic damaged area in the tensile specimen was simulated using FEM analysis. The analysis indicated that delamination would noticeably increase the fibre dominated stress at the edge of the hole, resulting in the specimen failure at lower loads than for an equivalent diameter machined hole.

For the shear tests, FEM analysis indicated that the shear stress in the laminate away from the centre of the specimen is significantly lower than at the centre and thus provided a correction factor to compare the strengths between specimens with ballistic damage off-centre and pristine specimens.

The characteristic distance approach developed by Tan [9-10] was adopted to predict the strength of the shear test specimens with a machined hole. For practical use, the results from this model were further fitted using a polynomial equation. This approach was extended to simulate strength of shear specimens with ballistic damage. The model fitted the measurement data well. Using this model, the ballistic impact from two 12.7 mm rounds was assessed to be equivalent to a single shot of 15.0 mm calibre in terms of the measured residual strength.

This work has developed the means to assess ballistic damage to thin-skinned carbon fibre polymer materials to support design, operation, and battle-damage repairs for military aircraft.

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